

COVID-19 KASALLIGIDAN KEYIN MIOKARDIT VA UNING PROFLAKTIKASI

Xolboboeva Shaxnoza Asadullaevna

Central Asian Medical University assistenti

Axmadjonova Diyorahon Oybekovna

Central Asian Medical University talabasi

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Annotation. Maqolada koronavirus pandemiyasi vaqti mobaynida shifoxonada davolangan 38 nafar bemorning davolash tajribasi jamlangan. Klinik ko'rinishlari, kechishi, diagnostik usullariga qarab muhokama qilingan va takliflar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: koronavirus, miokardit, angiotenzin sintezlovchi ferment 2, kardiomiotsitlar.

Аннотация. В статье обобщен опыт лечения 38 пациентов, находившихся в стационаре во время пандемии коронавируса. Обсуждены клинические проявления, течение, методы диагностики и даны предложения.

Ключевые слова: коронавирус, миокардит, ангиотензинсинтезирующий фермент 2, кардиомиоциты.

Annotation. The article summarizes the treatment experience of 38 patients treated in the hospital during the coronavirus pandemic. Clinical manifestations, course, diagnostic methods were discussed and suggestions were given.

Key words: Coronavirus, myocarditis, angiotensin synthesizing enzyme 2, cardiomyocytes.

Koronavirus pandemiyasi vaqtida COVID-19 virusi tomonidan turli darajalarda asoratlar bilan kechmoqda. Ayniqsa yurak-qon tomir sistemasining yallig'lanish bilan kechayotgan asoratlari ko'p uchrayotgani bu kasallik asoratlariga jiddiy qarash kerakligini ko'rsatmoqda. COVID-19 kasalligining yangi shtamlari inson organizimi turli a'zolariga xususan yurak mushaklariga yetkazayotgan ta'siri sezilarli darajada oshganligi bu kasallik asoratlariga va davolash taktikasiga xamda proflaktikasiga jiddiy qarash kerakligini ko'rsatmoqda. Buning asosiy sababi esa hozirgi vaqtda patogenezini to'liq o'rganilmagan, ammo virusning kardiomiotsitlarga bevosita zarar etkazuvchi ta'sirini taxmin qilish mumkin. Ushbu muammo zamonaviy tibbiyot uchun dolzarbdir va faol o'rganishni talab qilamoqda.

Tadqiqot maqsadi. Farg'ona shahar Meridian Klinik Diagnostik klinikasi kardiologiya bo'limida Koronavirus infeksiyasidan so'ng rivojlangan miokardit

bilan og'ri bilan og'ri kasallikning kechishi xamda rivojlanish mexanizmlarini kuzatish xamda proflaktik choralarini takomillashtirish.

Materiallar va usullar. SARS-CoV-2 infeksiyasidan kelib chiqqan o'tkir miokard shikastlanishi mexanizmi ACE2 bilan bog'liqlihi xaqida xorij adabiyotlarida ko'plab ma'lumotlar keltirilmoqda. Angiotenzin sintezlovchi ferment 2 (ACE2) yurak-qon tomir va immunitet tizimlarida muhim rol o'ynaydigan, fermenti membrana bilan bog'langan aminopeptidazadir. ACE2 SARS-CoV-2 uchun funktsional retseptor sifatida aniqlangan. SARS-CoV-2 infeksiyasi virusli oqsilning yurak va o'pkada ifodalangan ACE2 ga bog'lanishi natijasida yuzaga keladi, bu yurakning infeksiyaga ichki sezgirligini ko'rsatadi. Shuningdek, Koronavirus bilan kasallangan bemorlarning 35 foizida miokardda SARS-CoV genomi mavjudligini ko'rsatadigan ma'lumotlar mavjud, bu virus tomonidan kardiomiotsitlarga to'g'ridan-to'g'ri zarar etkazish ehtimolini oshiradi.

Farg'ona shaxar Meridian Klinik Diagnostik Hospital klinikasi kardiologiya bo'limida Koronavirus infeksiyasidan so'ng rivojlangan miokardit bilan xastalangan 38 ta bemorning 23 nafari (62.2%) ayollar va 15 nafari (37.8%) erkak bemorlarda daslabki kasallik bilan xastalanganidan so'ng daslabki 2 oy ichida kasallik rivojlanganligi aniqlandi.

Bu bemorlarning 24 tasi(73%) surunkali yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari bilan "D" kardiolog nazoratda turib doimiy ravishda davolanib kelgan. 14 (27%)nafari bemor esa kasallik Koronavirus kasalligini bilan xastalanganidan so'ng miokardit alomatlari aniqlanib davolanish uchun bizning shifoxonaga murojat qilishgan. Koronavirus kasalligi 10(27%) nafar (yengil o'pka zararlanishi 10-15%), 25 (67.6%)nafari, o'rta og'ir darajasi bilan (o'pka zararlanishi bilan-25-40%),og'ir darajasi bilan 2 nafar (o'pka zararlanishi 50-75%) xastalanib davolanishgan.Davolanishlarning 17 (46%) nafari statsionar sharoitda , 20(54%) ambulator sharoitda yoki mutaxasis nazoratisiz uy sharoitida davolanishgan.Ammo ikkala gurux bemorlarda Koronavirus kasalligi bilan xastalangan vaqtda miokardit belgilari kuzatilmagan va bezovta qilmagan. Kasallik alomatlari COVID-19 kasalligidan keyin 2-3 xaftasida namoyon bo'lgan.

Natijalar. Raqamlar shuni ko'rsatmoqdaki koronavirus kasalligi bilan kasallanish darajasidan qat'iy nazar yurak mushaklarining zararlanish darajasi orasida sezilarli farq yo'qligini ko'rsatmoqda. Kasallik asosan uy sharoitida va mutaxasis nazoratida qat'iy davo standartlari asosida davolanmagan bemorlar orasida tafovut borligi ko'rinmoqda.Bundan tashqari surunkali yurak-qon tomir kasalligi bilan xastalangan bemorlarda miokardit uchrash chastotasi

yuqoriligicha qolmoqda. E'tiborli tomoni miokardit kasalligi yurak-qon tomir kasalligi bilan xastalanmagan insonlar orasida xam uchrayotganidir. COVID-19 bilan xastalangan surunkali yurakqon tomir kasalliklari bilan kasallanmagan bemorlarni xam nazoratga olishni taqazo etmoqda.

Xulosa va tavsiyalar:

1. COVID-19 kasalligining qaysi darajasi bo'lishidan qat'iy nazar davolanish ishlarini mutaxasis nazoratida olib borish;
2. Davolash davomida xamda davolanish tugagandan so'ng albatta EKG va kardiolog ko'rivi;
3. Imkon qadar surunkali kasalliklari bo'lgan bemorlar COVID-19 kasalligini qaysi darajasida bo'lishidan qat'iy nazar, statsionar sharoitida mutaxasislar nazoratida davolanish;
4. Bemorlarda Angiotenzin sintezlovchi ferment 2 (ACE2) laborator sharoitda nazorat qilib boorish.

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